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Executive Summary of White Paper (5000 character limit)

The Large Synoptic Survey Telescope (LSST) is set to begin commissioning its instruments in 2021, with science verification commencing in 2022 and science operations in 2023. With its large field of view and 3.2 Gigapixel camera, it will scan 18,000 square degrees every few nights from 320-1050 nm. This cadence will not only build a deep co-added map of the sky to ~25th magnitude in its wide field and ~28th magnitude in its deep fields, but will enable transient science on the largest scale. It will produce millions of ‘alerts’ for bright new celestial objects each night. By the end of the nominal 11th data release, it will deliver 18 billion objects in 5.5 million images. LSST will revolutionize photometric survey science. There are a wide range of scientific collaborations under the LSST umbrella: the Stars, Milky Way and the Local Volume Collaboration, the Transients and Variable Stars Collaboration, the Dark Energy Science Collaboration, The Solar System Science Collaboration, The Active Galactic Nuclei Collaboration, the Strong Lensing Collaboration and the Informatics and Statistics Science Collaboration. We highlight the LSST science cases relevant to the Canadian community, and describe how LSST data will complement and transform science in these areas. In a separate white paper, we discuss the varied Canadian data access needs and LSST data products. We will describe how coordination with current and planned facilities and programs with Canadian participation and leadership, namely CFHT, CFIS/UNIONS, MSE, Gemini, and Euclid will leverage these science efforts even further. We discuss the proposed model for participation in LSST and motivate why a coordinated national strategy for Canadian data access is essential to ensuring both the continued Canadian scientific leadership in LSST, and how investing in the infrastructure and training necessary for LSST partnership would therefore be strategic for Canadian astronomy.

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LRP2020 White Paper

Science with the Large Synoptic Survey Telescope

THEMATIC AREAS (SCIENCE): Cosmology, Dark Energy, Dark Matter, Transient objects, Stellar evolution, Solar System science, Black Hole science

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1 Introduction

Observational astrophysics is moving from an era of detection and observation of novel events to a data-rich era. Large statistical samples from survey telescopes will mean that the coming decade will provide the astronomical community with an arsenal of data to answer fundamental questions in astronomy and cosmology:

- what drives the acceleration of the universe?
- what is the nature of dark matter?
- how do massive stars end their lives, and what are the optical counterparts to bursts of gravitational wave emission?
- how do galaxies grow and evolve with time, and how do the supermassive black holes at their centers grow?
- what is the structure of our own Galaxy?
- how do planets and planetary systems form and evolve?

The Large Synoptic Survey Telescope (LSST) is the next generation instrument to build up just such a large dataset. LSST was the top-ranked ground-based facility recommended in the U.S. Astro2010 decadal survey. Currently under construction on Cerro Pachón, Chile, it will reveal never-before-seen aspects of the sky in optical light. It will start its commissioning run in 2021, with scientific operations commencing in 2022, and will run for 10 years, with the possibility of extension.

LSST will scan the sky every few days in different filters, and by co-adding successive images over time, it will build a deeper image of the same patch of sky with less noise and ever-fainter objects becoming visible. Conversely, by measuring the differences between images taken on successive nights, it will discover astronomical transient events. These changing objects serve as light-beacons in the distant cosmos and also enable us to unravel the nature of cosmic explosions.

By the end of its ten-year mission, LSST will have observed 37 billion objects over the 18,000 square degrees of the sky visible from the northern Chilean desert and will have made 5.5 million images each 3.2 Gigapixels in size. It will be the most comprehensive survey of the night sky ever made in optical light, and will provide a wealth of information long after the nominal ten-year survey is complete. The depth and area of LSST data are shown in Figure 1, highlighting LSST's power in providing simultaneously unprecedented depth and area.

LSST will provide the astronomical community with a wealth of data that are useful to a variety of science cases and interests. We highlight some of the science cases below.

1.1 Cosmology with Type Ia supernovae from LSST

LSST will generate 10 million alerts about relatively bright objects in the sky *every night*. Many of these will be signatures of the characteristic brightening and fading ‘light curve’ of Type Ia supernovae, the cosmic markers with which the expansion of the universe is measured. Even after placing restrictions on the quality of the observed light curves, LSST will detect an estimated 300,000 supernovae over the ten-year survey, to measure cosmic distances with exquisite precision. Supernova distances illuminate the nature of the cosmic component of dark energy driving the accelerating expansion of the universe, visible through the stretching of distances to these bright beacons. The metric used to quantify how well an experiment can constrain the dark energy is called the Dark Energy Task Force Figure of Merit (FoM), which quantifies the decrease of uncertainty on the dark energy parameters. LSST will improve this FoM by over a factor of 10 compared to current experiments, opening up the window on cosmic dark energy and the fundamental question of why the universe is expanding at an ever-increasing rate.

1.2 Wide-field survey of bright transients and variables with LSST

In addition to populations of supernovae for dark energy science, the repeated LSST observations of both its deep and wide fields will generate orders of magnitude more transients of other types, if detected and followed up correctly. LSST should see many more of these interesting transients and variables (Drout et al., 2014). Optimizing the LSST observation plan for the detection of rapidly evolving (and some peculiar) transients is currently underway; see, e.g., white papers by Bianco et al. (2019) and Brandt et al. (2018). Multiwavelength studies of these transients (using facilities such as the SKA, eRosita, Fermi) will help us to identify unusual objects such as the white dwarf pulsar AR Sco Marsh et al. (2016), transitional millisecond pulsars (e.g. Bassa et al., 2014), and tidal disruption events (e.g. Auchettl et al., 2017).

1.3 Targeted and serendipitous discovery of gravitational wave counterparts

The detection of both gravitational waves (GW) and their electromagnetic counterparts are some of the highlights of science in this decade; the next decade will be one of routine and frequent detection yielding large samples of GW events and their use as cosmological tools to understand gravity. LSST will respond to Target of Opportunity (ToO) calls from GW observatories (see the recent LSST white paper by Margutti et al., 2019, optimizing LSST ToO science). Serendipitous discoveries by LSST of GW sources below the nominal detection limit of GW observatories will generate tens to hundreds of new discoveries (Setzer et al., 2019), and allow for calibration of the noise properties of gravitational wave detectors.

1.4 Building up supermassive black holes

Every sufficiently large galaxy harbors a supermassive black hole (SMBH) at its center, with a mass a million or a billion times that of the Sun. The mass of a SMBH is tightly correlated with certain properties of the surrounding galaxy, suggesting that outflows of matter and radiation from growing SMBHs regulate the growth of the host galaxy by shutting down its star formation. Understanding how SMBHs accrete matter and grow is therefore important for understanding massive galaxy evolution, as well as for its own sake. When a SMBH feeds on gas and grows in mass, it does so as a quasar - a disk of matter bigger than the solar system and hotter than the Sun, surrounded by in-flowing and out-flowing gas and visible from across the universe. How such disks emit radiation and launch winds cannot be studied directly (they are too far away to see such detail), but they can be studied in the time domain with reverberation mapping (RM). RM uses changes in brightness to measure light travel time and therefore physical size. The long-term repeated photometry in multiple filters in the LSST Deep Drilling Fields (DDFs) will be a bonanza for RM campaigns using spectroscopy to determine the dynamical structure of gas inflow and outflow near SMBHs. LSST will also enable photometric RM for basic size measurements of much larger samples (e.g., Chelouche et al. 2014), including rare subtypes of quasars which may be ‘Rosetta Stones’ for understanding inflows and outflows in quasars in general (e.g., Hall et al. 2011, Hall et al. 2013). The less intensive LSST time-domain observations of quasars outside the DDFs will illuminate quasar accretion, especially

through the early discovery of Changing-Look quasars (e.g., MacLeod et al. 2019). Changing-Look quasars are rare cases where a quasar’s brightness varies by up to a factor of ten within a few years, which can result in the quasar completely losing or gaining some of its spectral features. A dramatic change in the mass accretion rate has emerged as the leading explanation for these objects (e.g., Runnoe et al. 2016). The timescale for variations in these objects is much shorter than the standard theoretical timescale for accretion rate changes. Changing-Look quasars may provide the first concrete advance in accurately modelling quasar accretion disks in over 40 years, thanks to LSST systematically unearthing thousands of examples as they transition from one level of accretion to another.

1.5 Probing the nature of dark matter with LSST data

The fundamental nature of dark matter remains one of the biggest open questions in physics. While the evidence for unseen matter from observations of the dynamics of galaxies, clusters of galaxies, and the large-scale structure of the Universe is incontrovertible, little progress on the question “What is dark matter?” has been made in the 85 years since dark matter was first discovered. LSST, originally known as the “Dark Matter Telescope,” will allow fundamentally new observations of the small-scale structure of the dark matter distribution in the Milky Way that probe a wide variety of dark matter models (Drlica-Wagner et al. 2019). Studies with LSST of the Milky Way satellite galaxies and stellar streams will detect and characterize the smallest dark matter halos (e.g., Bovy et al. 2017), probing the minimum mass of ultra-light dark matter and thermal warm dark matter models. Measurements using stellar streams and stars in the Milky Way halo of the radial density profile and shape of the dark matter halo will be sensitive to self-interacting dark matter models, such as hidden sector and dark photon models (e.g., Bovy et al. 2016).

1.6 Weak Gravitational Lensing

Weak gravitational lensing of background sources by cosmic structure generates a shear distortion of galaxy shapes. Because the dark-matter dominated structure evolves with cosmic time, and this evolution depends on the expansion history, measurements of cosmic shear provide a powerful test of General Relativity, the dark sector and the cosmological parameters. The default lensing analysis for LSST’s DESC will be a tomographic analysis of this shear signal and the cross correlation of the signal with the galaxy overdensities. This ‘3x2 point’ analysis will include the shear-shear, galaxy-shear, and galaxy-galaxy correlations, the current standard in the field of weak lensing. This approach allows for the marginalization of both astrophysical and observational systematic uncertainties in the shear signal. LSST will improve the dark energy figure of merit from current constraints by an order of magnitude from *weak lensing measurements alone*.

1.7 Solar System discoveries and science

LSST will vastly increase our inventory of potentially hazardous Near Earth asteroids. In combination with the vast historical imaging database of the Canada-France-Hawaii telescope, it has the potential to do the same for several other types of solar system objects that are currently rare but scientifically invaluable, namely:

- *Earth Trojan asteroids*: orbits near Earth’s L4 and L5 Lagrange points can be stable for billions of years. Only one Earth Trojan is known (2010 TK7, estimated size 300 meters), but hundreds more like it could exist. Earth Trojans have low velocities relative to Earth, so they will be ideal targets for spacecraft missions for scientific study and resource extraction.
- *Interstellar Interlopers*: the objects ’Oumuamua, discovered in 2017 (Meech et al., 2017) and Borisov, discovered in 2019, are the first known asteroid and comet, respectively, from outside our Solar System. Dozens of other interstellar interlopers will likely be found by LSST. Triggered followup and archival searches will be critical to the science exploitation of such objects.
- *Active Asteroids*: some asteroids have unexpectedly been found to exhibit out-gassing activity, blurring the distinction between them and comets and providing new information on the abundance of volatiles such as

water ice in the asteroid belt and thus the early Solar System. Indeed, how this ice has avoided sublimation since the epoch of formation remains unknown.

- *Outer Solar System Planetesimals*: LSST will provide the conclusive catalog of the contents of the outer solar system (the Kuiper belt and beyond) with the expected discovery of over 40,000 objects in this region. This will provide a systematic inventory of the very interesting denizens of the outer Solar System, like apsidally aligned distant objects, where the alignments provide the key pieces of evidence for the presence of the purported Planet 9 (e.g., Sheppard & Trujillo 2016). LSST will test if the alignments are merely an observational bias (e.g., Shankman et al. 2017) or a real signal. Inventories of this region of the solar system will provide stringent constraints on the dynamical evolution of the giant planets and the processes of planetesimal and planetary system formation.

2 Connection and relevance to Canada

Link to the PIs above and the broad interests of the Canadian community to different types of the science. Discussion on the data access white paper by Fraser.

The LSST has many synergies with future astronomical facilities in which Canada is already invested. For example, cosmological studies with wide-area galaxy catalogs benefit from the extended wavelength coverage offered within the expected several thousand square degrees of overlap between the proposed space-based Cosmological Advanced Survey Telescope for Optical and ultraviolet Research (CASTOR, *UV, g, and u*; Côte et al. 2012), the LSST (optical to near-infrared, *ugrizy*), and the European Space Agency’s Euclid mission (near-infrared, *YJH*; Racca et al. 2016). In particular, photometric redshift estimates will be significantly improved by the combination of these data sets, which in turn will enhance the scientific products (e.g., Sorba & Sawicki 2011; Graham et al. 2019, submitted).

Another example is the unique opportunities for follow-up of LSST transients and variables with current ground-based observatories such as Gemini South (which is located adjacent to LSST) and next-generation facilities such as the Mauna Kea Spectroscopic Explorer (MSE) and the Thirty Meter Telescope (TMT). With its efficient scheduling, Gemini is ideally suited for LSST transient follow-up. This will be dramatically enhanced by the NSF-funded Gemini in the Era of Multi-Messenger Astronomy (GEMMA¹) project now under development. Additionally, Gemini-S will commission SCORPIO (Spectrograph and Camera for Observations of Rapid Phenomena in the Infrared and Optical Robberto et al., 2018), a simultaneous 8-channel imaging spectrograph designed specifically to optimize rapid follow-up of interesting transients and variables found by LSST. Finally, Gemini-N will provide the ability to follow-up transients for several crucial hours after they are no longer observable from Chile. In the longer term, the opportunity to routinely place MSE fibres on LSST transients/variables and/or their host galaxies would enable spectroscopic follow-up *en masse*. Even the random assignment of spare fibres to transient follow-up can have a major research impact. A similar endeavor, the Time-Domain Extragalactic Survey (TiDES) is planned during 4MOST operations to obtain up to 30,000 spectra of transients and variables from the LSST and other surveys (Swann et al., 2019). The TMT in particular was designed to enable a fast response for rapid target-of-opportunity observations: <10 minutes, including the change to any of its instruments (TMT International Observatory, 2018). This capability, along with the unprecedented depth and resolution of the TMT, is expected to provide breakthroughs in our understanding of extragalactic explosions (e.g., Graham 2018; Graham et al. 2019). Similarly, LSST light curves of known variables including stars and AGN will both identify and extend the photometric baseline (in time and wavelength) for cadenced surveys of such sources, for example with CASTOR and MSE. These synergies will enhance the science return from all of these facilities

¹<https://www.gemini.edu/gemma/index.html>

Figure 1: Current and future surveys shown as a function of survey depth and area. LSST will provide a simultaneously deep and wide survey. Optimization of the survey cadence is ongoing and will remove some of the large filter gaps between observations. Figure reproduced from Scolnic et al. (2018)

3 Timeline

LSST is currently under construction and will begin commissioning in 2021, with science verification starting in 2022 and full science operations slated to begin in 2022².

3.1 LSST data products and releases

LSST will release different types or ‘levels’ of data products at different rates within the the project or to the broader international astronomical community.

- *Prompt data products*: These products are generated continuously every observing night from the scans and the differences between any image and a reference co-added image. These prompt data products ‘alert’ the community about objects that have either changed their brightness or position. These data products are released publicly with a 60-second latency from observations, while source catalogues derived from the difference images which include more information such as the orbital parameters for solar system objects, are released internally to the project within 24 hours.
- *Data Release data products*: The processed imaging and catalog data products will be released internally to project members annually and will include calibrated and co-added images with their measured positions, fluxes and shapes, variability information and a compact description of a light curve in the case of transient or variable objects. Two years after release within the project, LSST will provide world-wide public data releases. The Data Release data products will include a uniform reprocessing of the difference-imaging-based Prompt data products, that were previously released on a shorter latency.
- *User Generated data products*: These products will originate from the community or stakeholders and project teams or collaborations, and will either be stored as Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) that will be provided by the LSST Data Management System, or as part of the LSST Science Platform which will enable

²The timeline of the LSST project is updated on a regular basis online at this link.

processing of the data for various analyses. User Generated data products are not necessarily included in the world-wide data releases. The interests of the Canadian community in particular LSST data products is described in detail in a companion LRP White paper.

3.2 LSST Data Rights

Until May 2019, LSST was operating under a system where access to data releases was restricted to those partners with LSST Data Rights, typically obtained through Memoranda of Agreement between the LSST Corporation and international partners, while the prompt data products are made immediately public to the world. In the section below, we discuss the history of Canadian efforts to obtain access to LSST, the current landscape and the future avenues for ensuring Canadian access to this ground-breaking survey.

4 Costs for LSST Data Access

In the Canadian context, an agreement was previously brokered through the Dunlap Institute and the University of Toronto, which created a consortium of Canadian scientists who would negotiate access co-funded by support from their own institutions or grants and support of the Dunlap Institute. In May 2019, a new framework was established as the US National Science Foundation (NSF) and Department of Energy (DOE) reached agreement on a new LSST Data Rights and Funding model. In this new model, they acknowledge the value of international partnerships for LSST but decided to revise the partnership model to focus on *in-kind contributions* instead of *monetary contributions*. LSST will still maintain the proprietary period for LSST data release and the open LSST alert stream with no proprietary period as previously planned, but the access will now be negotiated via in-kind contributions related to the LSST construction project or facility operations, data archiving and serving to the broader community (not restricted to any particular country or region), and/or related astrophysical (follow-up) resources as considered and agreed to jointly between the agencies and international partners. These discussions will be brokered by an LSST Resource Board, which will be described in the coming year. **This new model is an opportunity for national access to LSST for all Canadians.** A description of contributing a public data archive as an operational contribution to LSST in exchange for membership is provided in the white paper ‘E040: Canadian Participation in the LSST’ (Fraser et al.). The ‘take-home’ message is that the best approach for Canadian LSST access is through broad *national* support and negotiation, leveraging planned data infrastructure support and existing Canadian facilities and telescope resources.

To address Canadian access a two-pronged approach is being pursued. A Canadian Foundation for Innovation (CFI) application is being proposed to build the Canadian LSST Advanced Science Platform (CLASP) which will provide science analysis capabilities for LSST data to address the specific needs of Canadian astronomers, thereby enabling exploitation of both the data release and the prompt data products by Canadian astronomers. CLASP will substantially reduce the need for Canadian astronomers to access the LSST provisioned science platform for data access and thus lower the cost of entry for Canada to this project. In parallel, the CADM has approached the LSST Resource Board to consider the hosting of the LSST public data releases, and in particular, the imaging component of those releases, as an in-kind contribution for national level access to the LSST Survey. As the process of negotiating in-kind contributions to LSST is still underway (the formal process will only begin in October or November of 2019 with responses due by the end of March 2020) there are few specific details. However, a multi-petabyte storage system capable of distributing the public LSST DRs is seen by the LSST Resources Board as a significant contribution to the project. Such a facility would be coupled to and enhance the capabilities of “CLASP” and is budgetarily competitive with the anticipated costs of national buy-in to LSST.

5 Description of risk

The risks of inaction cannot be overstated. LSST will be *the most important photometric survey instrument for the coming decade and beyond*, and will be an essential complement to current and planned spectroscopic survey

facilities in Canada. Losing proprietary access to data catalogues and the associated science analysis tools and platforms will mean that Canada lags behind scientifically from the US and its international LSST partners. In addition, *access* to the data products and the computational resources to process them will not be possible without a coordinated strategy within Canada. These data are too large to follow the approach of the past of downloading a catalog and running analysis on one's own computers. These data analyses will have to happen *in situ* on servers that host the LSST data.

6 Governance/membership structure

Before May 2019, when Canadian participation in LSST was envisaged to proceed via cash contributions, a Canadian LSST Consortium structure was established, which would have resulted in a Canadian LSST board to allocate PI positions as a function of institutional buy in to LSST. Pending decisions by the US funding agencies on LSST international participation, such a structure could readily be established to allocate PI slots and manage Canadian LSST membership, while striving for national access however possible.

7 Summary

LSST will revolutionize science from dark energy studies to measurements of solar system objects, and will be the foremost photometric surveys of the coming decade. Ensuring Canadian participation in LSST and access to the rich datasets that will result will power Canadian science well beyond the 2020s, and will lead to significant numbers highly qualified personnel with skills that are readily transferable to the data science and machine learning communities, which are strategic areas of investment in Canada.

1: How does the proposed initiative result in fundamental or transformational advances in our understanding of the Universe?

LSST will go deeper over a wider area (thousands of square degrees) with cadences of hours, days, weeks, months and years, than any previous telescope, building up images of as-yet-unseen galaxies and structures and our own Milky Way and related satellites. LSST's co-added images of the sky will probe the lensing of galaxies by cosmic structure and answer fundamental questions about dark matter and dark energy. Because LSST will scan the sky repeatedly, it will observe an unprecedented number of astronomical transients and variables, which will revolutionize studies of cosmic acceleration, stellar death and evolution. And LSST's catalog of solar system objects will be the constraining input into understanding the formation of our planetary system.

2: What are the main scientific risks and how will they be mitigated?

The biggest scientific risk is that Canadians will not have access to LSST data without a coordinated national policy for data access. This means that we would not be able to use LSST as a data set to cross correlate with existing data sets at other wavelengths, nor would we be able to use Canadian facilities to obtain, e.g., spectroscopic follow up of interesting objects.

3: Is there the expectation of and capacity for Canadian scientific, technical or strategic leadership?

Canadian participation to date has been limited to the 15 PIs who form part of the Canadian LSST Consortium through the initial Dunlap support. These Canadian PIs, however have been active in many of the LSST Science Collaborations, including the Dark Energy Science Collaboration (DESC) and the Transients and Variable Stars (TVS), the Active Galactic Nuclei (AGN), the Solar System, and the Stars, Milky Way, and Local Volume

science collaborations. In particular, authors of this white paper have played significant scientific leadership roles in the TVS, DESC and Solar System groups. Data science as a technical field is growing rapidly, and has natural synergies with Artificial Intelligence, an area of acknowledged Canadian expertise and focus. The data management, software, and analysis required to extract science from the formidable LSST information stream will require innovative solutions that are expected to have broader impacts in the tech sector. Investing in the infrastructure and training necessary for LSST partnership would therefore be strategic for Canadian astronomy.

4: Is there support from, involvement from, and coordination within the relevant Canadian community and more broadly?

While LSST was not supported by the Long Range Plan in 2010, the Canadian science community has evolved in the past decade, and support for LSST science continues to grow. For example, a series of new faculty hires across Canada have increased the interest and involvement in LSST science.

5: Will this program position Canadian astronomy for future opportunities and returns in 2020-2030 or beyond 2030?

LSST will be **the** photometric survey of the coming decade, and all other optical surveys will complement its wide and deep look at the sky. We discuss wide-field astronomy in Canada in a companion white paper, but it is worth noting here that current and planned facilities and programs with Canadian participation and leadership, namely CFHT, CFIS/UNIONS, MSE, Gemini, and Euclid will all be able to make great scientific use of LSST data. The building of the Canadian LSST Science Platform that will support CLASP and the public data archive will expand Canada's capacity and expertise in the handling of large astronomical datasets and further prepare us for participation in other planned large data projects in astronomy, such as the SKA.

6: In what ways is the cost-benefit ratio, including existing investments and future operating costs, favourable?

The cash cost for Canadian LSST contributions (calculated in 2019 US dollars, but what would have been paid for twelve years of operations) amounted to just over CAD 580K per PI over 12 years, including four additional co-I slots per PI for students and postdoctoral researchers engaged in LSST science. Assuming roughly 30 Canadian faculty who would use LSST data, that cost would be less than CAD 20 M for 150 people. The current costs are slightly harder to quantify given the change of data policy from financial contributions to in-kind contributions and the continued negotiations of those contributions. We would expect, however, the scale of the in-kind contribution would roughly match to the previously expected level of financial commitment (\$CAD 20M). This level of expenditure would gain national access and will be further leveraged by the building of CLASP. Given the very broad science impact for Canada (which currently has no access to an modern southern sky survey) the benefits of membership are very high.

7: What are the main programmatic risks and how will they be mitigated?

Construction for LSST is well underway, and science operations are on track to begin in 2023, after science commissioning and verification in 2021/2022. The programmatic risks right now are the uncertainty in the LSST Data Rights and Access policy. These policies will be made clear on a short timescale, but will be mitigated by developing a national strategy for Canadian LSST access as soon as possible.

8: Does the proposed initiative offer specific tangible benefits to Canadians, including but not limited to interdisciplinary research, industry opportunities, HQP training, EDI, outreach or education?

LSST as a project has an extensive program of skills development in Data Science and analysis, through the LSST Data Science Fellowship, which is open to Canadian students. Similar fellowships can be developed here in Canada, to prepare young people for data access. Similarly, as part of the above-mentioned CFI proposal, a strategy to train and equip postdoctoral researchers in the skills and techniques that will enable the serving and processing of LSST data will result in many transferable skills. In addition to a HQP training program, LSST has a broad mandate for Education and outreach, including an LSST project office for EPO, and Canadian students have already benefited from LSST-supported training workshops. Through Canadian leadership in an LSST-funded science initiative^a, we reached out to thousands of data scientists and groups with diverse scientific interests.

^aThe PLAsTiCC project: www.plasticc.org.

References

- Auchettl, K., Guillochon, J., & Ramirez-Ruiz, E. 2017, *ApJ*, 838, 149
- Bassa, C. G., Patruno, A., Hessels, J. W. T., et al. 2014, *MNRAS*, 441, 1825
- Bianco, F. B., Drout, M. R., Graham, M. L., et al. 2019, *PASP*, 131, 068002
- Bovy, J., Bahmanyar, A., Fritz, T. K., & Kallivayalil, N. 2016, *ApJ*, 833, 31
- Bovy, J., Erkal, D., & Sanders, J. L. 2017, *MNRAS*, 466, 628
- Brandt, W. N., Ni, Q., Yang, G., et al. 2018, arXiv e-prints, arXiv:1811.06542
- Chelouche, D., Shemmer, O., Cotlier, G. I., Barth, A. J., & Rafter, S. E. 2014, *ApJ*, 785, 140
- Côte, P., Scott, A., Balogh, M., et al. 2012, in *Proc. SPIE*, Vol. 8442, *Space Telescopes and Instrumentation 2012: Optical, Infrared, and Millimeter Wave*, 844215
- Drlica-Wagner, A., Mao, Y.-Y., Adhikari, S., et al. 2019, arXiv e-prints, arXiv:1902.01055
- Drout, M. R., Chornock, R., Soderberg, A. M., et al. 2014, *ApJ*, 794, 23
- Graham, M. 2018, *LSST & TMT: Data Infrastructures for Time Domain Astronomy*, doi:10.5281/zenodo.2209001
- Graham, M., Milisavljevic, D., Rest, A., et al. 2019, *BAAS*, 51, 339
- Hall, P. B., Anosov, K., White, R. L., et al. 2011, *MNRAS*, 411, 2653
- Hall, P. B., Brandt, W. N., Petitjean, P., et al. 2013, *MNRAS*, 434, 222
- MacLeod, C. L., Green, P. J., Anderson, S. F., et al. 2019, *ApJ*, 874, 8
- Margutti, R., Metzger, B. D., Chornock, R., et al. 2019, *ApJ*, 872, 18
- Marsh, T. R., Gänsicke, B. T., Hümmelich, S., et al. 2016, *Nature*, 537, 374
- Meech, K. J., Weryk, R., Micheli, M., et al. 2017, *Nature*, 552, 378
- Racca, G. D., Laureijs, R., Stagnaro, L., et al. 2016, in *Proc. SPIE*, Vol. 9904, *Space Telescopes and Instrumentation 2016: Optical, Infrared, and Millimeter Wave*, 990400
- Robberto, M., Roming, P. W., van der Horst, A. e. J., et al. 2018, in *Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series*, Vol. 10702, *Proc. SPIE*, 107020I
- Runnoe, J. C., Cales, S., Ruan, J. J., et al. 2016, *MNRAS*, 455, 1691
- Scolnic, D., Kessler, R., Brout, D., et al. 2018, *ApJ*, 852, L3
- Setzer, C. N., Biswas, R., Peiris, H. V., et al. 2019, *MNRAS*, 485, 4260
- Shankman, C., Kavelaars, J. J., Bannister, M. T., et al. 2017, *AJ*, 154, 50
- Sheppard, S. S., & Trujillo, C. 2016, *AJ*, 152, 221
- Sorba, R., & Sawicki, M. 2011, *Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific*, 123, 777
- Swann, E., Sullivan, M., Carrick, J., et al. 2019, *The Messenger*, 175, 58
- TMT International Observatory. 2018, *TMT Observatory Architecture Document*